

Diasporic Elements in Jhumpa Lahiri's *The Namesake*

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Abstract

*In the fast globalized world, Diaspora issues, cultural identity, are enriching the Diaspora literature in the twenty- first century. The Diaspora elements are recurrent themes in the writings of Salman Rushdie, Amitav Ghosh, V.S. Naipaul, Kiran Desai, Bharati Mukherjee, Jhumpa Lahiri and many others. Diasporic fiction lingers over alienation, loneliness, rootlessness, homelessness, nostalgia, protest, assertions and quest for identity. It also addresses issues related to amalgamation or disintegration of cultures, discriminating margins of two different social milieus, internalizing longing and suffering forced amnesia. Jhumpa Lahiri is a voice of Indian Diasporas in America. She takes up the issue of the impact of exile and immigration on the complexity of life as pitched against deviating ethnic, religious and cultural backgrounds. In her debut novel, *The Namesake* (2003), she handles these complexities of the immigrants' experiences in lucidly.*

Keywords: diasporic, exile, nostalgia, immigration, deviating.

The word ‘diasporic’ has been taken from the Greek *dia*, meaning to scatter. It gives the sense of dispersal through space. The term ‘Diaspora’ referred to the Jewish Community, which was without a state of its own and faced discrimination and oppression all over the world. However, the term became popular and was used in the context of other nationalities also which was displaced from the original homelands due to one reason or the other. Even though the distinction has to make between the forced and willing movement of people, the phenomenon of diaspora necessarily involves a “structure of location followed by dislocation and relocation” (Paranjape 59). Moving away from one’s homeland and setting elsewhere on a long-term basis does mean dislocation that brings in the sense of loss and nostalgia. This was following by a bid for relocation in an alien milieu through negotiation and adjustment. All such Indians who have been living outside India constitute the Indian diaspora. Having born of educated middle class Bengali parents in London and grown up in Rhodes Island (USA), Jhumpa Lahiri beautifully and genuinely portrays the diaspora experiences in her first collection of short stories, *Interpreter of Maladies* (which won her the Pulitzer Prize for fiction in 2000), again doing an encore in her first novel, *The Namesake*, grabbing instant recognition and also a piece of cinematic history. Prior to going into details of the plot to discuss the theme of diasporic conflict of dual identity in *The Namesake*, it would be helpful to mention Lahiris’s remarks. In an interview

released by Houghton Mifflin Company Lahiri says that the novel is definitely about those “who are culturally displaced or those who grow up in two worlds simultaneously.” Talking about the predicament of immigrants Jhumpa Lahiri says: “I think that for immigrants the challenges of exile, the loneliness, the constant sense of alienation, and the knowledge of and longing for a lost world, are more explicit and distressing than for their children.”

The novel has an autobiographical line as Lahiri’s experience of growing up as a child of immigrants resembles that of her protagonist, is Gogol. In an interview with Mira Nair, she says: “I wanted to please my parents and meet their expectations. I also wanted to meet the expectations of my American peers, and the expectations I put on myself to fit into American society. It’s a classic case of divided identity.” Like Gogol, her pet name involuntarily became her name. She has two other names on her passport and her birth certificate. When she has been enrolled in school, the teachers decided that Jhumpa was the easiest of her to pronounce. Talking about the diasporic crisis of dual identity Lahiri, in the same interview, reflects: “The original spark of the book was the fact that a friend of my cousin in India had a pet name, Gogol. I wanted to write about a pet name distinction for a long time. It is almost too perfect a metaphor for the experience of growing up as the child of immigrants, having a divided identity, divided loyalties etc.” In a conversation with Mira Nair, Lahiri says, “The names we have, there is so much about them: Who are they and we are and are the one world that exists that represents us. And yet we don’t choose them. They are from our parents.”

As identity becomes the core issue, names become quite significant. The expressive function of a name varies from culture to culture. They have given the two names for Bengali children: one that is a pet name used only by family and close friends, and others that is a good name, used by the rest of the humanity. This very feeling of dual identity has been very well portrayed in the character of Gogol. At birth, Gogol is given a pet name as his official name sent in a letter from his great grandmother in India, gets lost in the mail. His parents give him the surname of the Russian writer Nikolai Gogol as the first name in the Massachusetts hospital where he is born. The chosen name with the accepting that it is merely a formality, and will in time become just a pet name. Gogol, the name of his father’s favourite writer, goes on the birth certificate and stays with him in his early school years. Upon entering Kindergarten, Gogol is told by his family that he is to be called Nikhil, a good name, by the teachers and other children at school. Gogol discards his proper name and wants to be called Gogol by society as well as his family.

This decision made on the first day of nursery school causes him years of distress as it was also his first attempt to reject a dual identity. As a child, he does not question who he is; he “doesn’t mind his name. It seems perfectly normal.” (p. 66). As he grows up, he begins to question who he is. The fact that Gogol, as a child was aware of the importance of identity, which is revealed by the field visit of his class to the graveyard where other children located the graves of the members of their clan by the surname mentioned in the epitaph, but to his dismay, he could not find any ‘Ganguli’ buried there (p 91). His first name ‘Gogol’ did not relate him to either the Indian Community or the American and so it dampened his spirits. He

spends his teenage and young adult years for trying to discover his identity. Before his departure for college, Gogol officially changes his name to Nikhil, which is symbolic of his self-conscious attempts to completely disown his real self and tries to metamorphose himself to a different persona. But even though he had longed to change his name, he finds that he has to get used to being called Nikhil. When his parents also refer to him as Nikhil; he feels, “...in that instant that he is not related to them, not their child.”(p.106)

However, Gogol spends his life living in the United States where children are ashamed of their difference from others. Though Gogol and his sister Sonali are born and raised in the U.S., they feel the annoyance of being different from most of the kids they know. Some mock their names; some spoil their mailbox with derogatory terms and some just find them funny. During adolescence, Gogol desires to blend in American society and to live unnoticed. Other Americans never view him an American, however, even though he is a native- born citizen. This living ‘in-between’ situation

is painful and marginalizing for the diasporas. The identities of diaspora persons and communities can neither be placed only about some fatherland to which they all long to return nor to that country alone where they settle down. They, by all means, face the crisis of hybrid or dual identity, which makes their existence all the more difficult. This is experience universal to all Indian diaspora, irrespective of their caste, region and religion (which they so strongly and devotedly clung to during their stay in India).

For the second generation, the question of identity is a complicated issue. At home, Indian culture and value system are adhered to, while in public the American code of conduct is followed. This is become even more difficult. When Gogol attends a panel discussion about Indian novels written in English, the discussion centres on the identity problem of ABCD:

Teleologically speaking, ABCDs are unable
to answer the question ‘where are you from?’
the sociologist on the panel declares.
(The Namesake, 118)

Gogol realizes that ABCD [American Born Confused Desi] refers to him also. He ponders over the question of distinctiveness. Despite his parents’ efforts to keep him “Indianized” Gogol started mimic his American friends in rustiness and aping them in every aspect. For example, his parents didn’t know about him secretly smoking with his friends, or going to late-night parties. However, he still manages to get good grades and gets into Yale University. There, to his horror and utter disdain, he learns about his namesake, Nikolai Gogol, that he was a cerebral pariah and starts to hate his name. Because of this, he changes it to Nikhil to distance himself from all the bindings of his family and shun all their expectations. He gets attached to a white American girl, Ruth but they soon divide after Ruth spends both spring and summer terms in England studying literature. This constant struggle for finding out the identity is beautifully portrayed in the novel, as first-generation immigrants and their children struggle to find their moorings in an adopted society. On the one hand, the Ganguli parents, especially Ashima, with adapting to a different culture than they are used to, on the other hand, their children (Gogol and Sonia) fight back to achieve an improbable synthesis between respect for their progenitor’s roots and the lure of a more liberating American society. The identities of Diaspora individuals and communities cannot be placed only in solitary reference to some homeland to which they all passionately long to return nor to that country alone which they have made their own. They, in the exercise of their means and ends, wilfully face the challenges thrown by the crisis of hybrid or dual identity, which makes their existence all the more fluid. After his break-up with Ruth, Gogol has an affair with Maxine, an Anglo-Saxon American ethnicity and a member of a liberal and very wealthy Manhattan family. He starts to live with her family and gets closer to her family and moves away from his own. Although they love each other, they eventually break up when Gogol returns after completing all the Bengali rituals on his father’s death. They fight over Gogol’s struggles regarding the emotional complications related to his father’s death. In a slight twist in the tale, Gogol’s mothers Ashima Suggests Gogol meet Moushumi, the daughter of one of her friends belonging to another Bengali family mainly, due to their shared cultural background. Gogol knew Moushumi from his childhood. She had the unfortunate experience of having planned a wedding only to have her future groom to change his mind at the last minute. Gogol was reluctant to meet Moushumi for two reasons. Firstly, for common cultural roots, i.e. being Bengali and then for her disgraced past. But he hardly had any choice as he had to meet her anyway, to please his mother. They meet at a bar and develop intimacy.

Although it was a blind date engineered by their mothers, they develop a liking for each other and eventually settle in matrimony. During a party, there starts a discussion on names. Moushumi’s name explained as a “damp south westerly breeze” (p 240). It is revealed at this point by Moushumi that Nikhil had changed his name. Gogol had not expected her to blurt out the secret. “He stares at her, stunned, have never told her not to tell anyone. He assumed she never would. His expression lost on her; she smiles back at him, unaware of what she’s done. The dinner guests regarded him; their mouth hanging open in confused smiles” (p 243). This episode inevitably leads to his former

name Gogol and even though another guest Sally can place the name as belonging to the writer of short story 'Overcoat,' others including Donald consider it a queer name.

Gogol slowly gets disillusioned with Moushumi. The scent of her body which, intoxicated him seems now suppressed by the stale smell of smoke left behind by her excessive smoking. However, by the end of their first year of marriage, Moushumi has grown restless and begins to regret her decision to marry. Gogol suspects something foul and their marriage comes to an end when Moushumi starts having a sexual affair with her old love interest. Throughout the novel, the character Gogol changes in many different ways. Throughout his life, he tried to shed his parents' un-American lifestyle, but in the end, he succumbed to his past and ancestry. Ever since Gogol's childhood, all ever wanted was to find a place where he could fit in, whether it be in his own culture, or in the American one in which he lives. During his life, he searches everywhere to find out who he is and where he belongs. Even after his stay and frequent visits to India, he could never be a part of Indian culture. He could never be Indian as he was born and brought up here; at the same time, the name and the family values never let him be American. His multiple relationships with American girls were never successful, and his marriage with an Indian girl was also a disastrous failure. He always remains in a dilemma about his identity, and that is the reason he could never be the one he likes.

Although Gogol Ganguly had a harrowing time coming to terms with real self and accepting himself in his teenage and early adult years, he eventually turns the corner and discovers his identity at the end of the novel. Jhumpa Lahiri's denouement achieves a balance. By the end of the novel, Gogol feels comforted by one thing: before his father had died, he had revealed the real image for choosing that name for him. At thirty-two, finally proud of his name and its meaning, Nikhil Gogol Ganguly accepted his name and his fate. He realizes that his identity overstated by both cultures. He tries to find solace and a temporary reconciliation with his name and the inheritance he had rejected, as he turns to the book his father had gifted him on his birthday, which Lahiri symbolically mentions:

As the hours of the evening pass, he will grow distracted, anxious to return to his room, to be alone to read the book he had once forsaken, have abandoned until now. Until moments ago it was destined to disappear from his life altogether, but he has salvaged it by chance, as his father was pulled from a crushed train forty years ago. (p. 290) Academic Research Vol. 1, No. 1,3 Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic Research Vol. 1, No. 1, 3

The diasporic crisis of dual identity faced by Gogol gets resolved when he realizes that the answer is not to abandon or attempt to diminish either Indian or American culture, but to instruct the two together. He does not have to be one or the other; he does not have to choose. He is made up of both, and instead weakening his pride, his identity is strengthened by this. Coming out of his turmoil, Gogol can stand on his feet and is no longer ashamed of him. In American culture and values, and at the same time retaining his parents' Indian heritage, he feels that proud of his name Nikhil Gogol Ganguly and all that it means.

Through this novel Jhumpa Lahiri's deals Diaspora elements, multiculturalism, nostalgia, immigration, divergent of Indian Writing in English and relationship between sexes. Her concentration on narrative tends to be spatial rather than sequential, the depiction of protagonists, exploration of familial ties are portrayed or depicted here.

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